

MASARYK UNIVERSITY
FACULTY OF INFORMATICS

Semi-automatic tools for image segmentation

MASTER'S THESIS

Bc. Martin Moučka

Brno, Spring 2018

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Declaration

Hereby I declare that this paper is my original authorial work, which I have worked out on my own. All sources, references, and literature used or excerpted during elaboration of this work are properly cited and listed in complete reference to the due source.

Bc. Martin Moučka

Advisor: doc. RNDr. Petr Matula, Ph.D.

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Abstract

This thesis deals with tools for semi-automatic image segmentation. It describes some of the well known semi-automatic segmentation techniques. Practical part involves the development of an application for quick semi-automatic segmentation of a large number of images. We selected four semi-automatic methods, described them in detail and implemented them in the application. The application is easily extendible and allows adding more segmentation techniques. We tested implemented methods on different kinds of biomedical images in order to evaluate their practical usability. The amount of time needed to segment each image with each method was measured and outputs of each method were compared using Jaccard similarity coefficient.

Keywords

segmentation, semi-automatic segmentation, interactive graph cuts, grabcut, random walks, region growing, wxWidgets, image processing

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Introduction

Due to the development of technology, it is possible to acquire large amounts of image data of different kinds. One of these kinds are biomedical images that usually need to be further processed and analyzed. One of the first steps of image analysis is segmentation of objects captured in an image. Segmenting an image manually may be time-consuming, but automatic segmentation methods are still not perfect, therefore it could be convenient to use semi-automatic segmentation methods, where a user collaborating with a computer has more control over the result and at the same time, the computer helps to delimit boundaries of segmented objects. When the right method is used, a user should be able to reduce the amount of time needed for segmentation.

Another reason why it is necessary to quickly segment large amount of images is the increasing popularity of neural networks which can be also used for image segmentation. In order to work properly, neural networks have to be first trained on a large number of images, where it is also necessary to provide a correct segmentation result for each image, so-called *ground truth*. To acquire ground truths for a large dataset of training images, it is possible to segment each image manually, but it would be more comfortable to utilize a semi-automatic method which could speed up the segmentation process.

Writing this thesis involved the development of an application for fast semi-automatic segmentation of a large number of images. This application should be easily extendible with more semi-automatic methods.

The first chapter introduces image segmentation and possible segmentation approaches.

In the second chapter, semi-automatic segmentation is more closely described. Some of the well known methods are briefly mentioned and four methods, that are implemented in the application, are described in detail.

In the third chapter we describe the implementation of the application, its most important classes and their important methods. We also describe the functionality of the application and implemented segmentation techniques.

In the fourth chapter, we test implemented methods on different types of biomedical images and we compare their practical usability and time efficiency in comparison with manual segmentation.

The appendix contains a guide with code examples on how to extend the application with new segmentation techniques.

1 Image segmentation

Image segmentation is a process of dividing an image into regions, such that pixels in each region share some particular characteristics and each region has a meaning in the context of a given image. In the ideal case, regions obtained by segmentation should correspond to real-world objects contained in the image. The result of image segmentation could be a division of an image into foreground, typically area covered by a particular object or objects, and background. In this case we speak about binary segmentation. Another possible result is a division of an image into multiple regions corresponding to multiple objects, in which case the process is called K -ary segmentation. The output of image segmentation is an assignment of each pixel to a particular object, where each object is denoted by a label. In the case of binary segmentation, commonly used labels are 0 for background and 1 for foreground. In the case of K -ary segmentation, labels are $1 \dots K$, where K is the number of image objects.

Image segmentation has numerous applications including object extraction, boundary tracking, face detection, object tracking, and finds its usage in medicine, entertainment, as well as a broad range of industrial applications.

Image segmentation often plays a crucial role as the first step in complex image analysis or computer vision systems. The quality of resulting segmentation and performance of a segmentation algorithm highly affects the output of the whole system and if segmentation is performed properly, it streamlines consecutive stages of the system.

Based on what the used algorithm puts emphasis on, segmentation techniques are usually [5, 6, 12] classified as thresholding based techniques, region based techniques, edge based techniques, clustering techniques, and neural networks, although more sophisticated techniques frequently combine more approaches and are not possible to be assigned into a single class.

Another point of view from which we can classify segmentation techniques is based on the amount of user interaction with the segmentation system. From this perspective we classify segmentation techniques to manual, automatic and semi-automatic.

1.1 Manual segmentation

Manual segmentation refers to a process where a user manually marks regions in the image by drawing a border of object of interest or by another similar technique such as painting with a brush and marking area covered by a given object. This process is time consuming and if the image contains non-trivial content and structures e.g. of a medical character, requiring deeper understanding of the related field, segmentation often has to be performed by a trained expert, whose time could be better used on other tasks. An experienced researcher may spend two hours by segmenting a single structure from a MRI image of the brain and it may require more than a week to segment all main structures of the brain [26].

1.2 Automatic segmentation

Automatic segmentation techniques can segment images without user interaction. However, output of an automatic system depends on the suitability of the used segmentation technique for the type of the image we want to segment. The output also usually depends on one or more parameters of the segmentation algorithm. These parameters can either be estimated automatically by the algorithm itself or fine tuned by a user in order to obtain as good segmentation as possible.

2 Semi-automatic segmentation

Even though image segmentation has been the subject of research for decades, automatic methods are still not perfect. One of the reasons for this situation may lie in the definition of segmentation itself, which says that the purpose of segmentation is to find and label objects that are relevant in the given context. However, in order to recognize relevant objects, one has to first understand the context on higher level and it is not possible to suffice with image data itself. Understanding the context of an image is an ability that is closer to people than to computers.

Image segmentation can be viewed as a process with two phases: recognition and delimitation. Recognition means determining rough position of an object in an image and delimitation means precisely marking off the boundary of an object. Because humans can understand the image context, they are usually more successful in the recognition phase, than computer algorithms. On the other hand, computers usually outperform humans in marking off the object boundary [13].

The third possible approach to image segmentation, which combines the automatic and manual approaches and tries to take the best of each of them is called semi-automatic or interactive segmentation. It uses computer's ability to precisely delimit an object and combines it with the ability of a user that understands the image on the high level and can recognize individual relevant objects and their positions. Semi-automatic segmentation aims to overcome shortcomings of automatic segmentation, which may fail on objects with unclear boundaries, while it reduces the user interaction time.

2.1 The process of semi-automatic segmentation

The interactive segmentation system is typically composed of three components, which may be also understood as three steps that an interactive segmentation process could be decomposed to:

1. **User input**

A user provides an information, which helps the computer with the computation of segmentation.

2. **Computation**

A computer tries to delimit the objects based on the information provided in step 1.

3. **Display output**

A computer displays an intermediate segmentation that was computed in step 2.

These three steps can be iteratively repeated and the input can be edited until the user is not satisfied with the result. This way the human operator and the computer cooperate, where the computer has to interpret user's input. A very important prerequisite for the segmentation to be good and for the user interaction time to be minimized is that the user understands, how their input affects the computation and therefore the resulting segmentation.

A user can provide their input in various ways, commonly it is one of these kinds:

- **Initial segmentation**

A user provides an initial segmentation, which should ideally be close to the desired one.

- **Boundary indication**

A user provides information about the location of some parts of a boundary.

- **Object indication**

A user provides information about the position of objects or indicates, where foreground and background parts are.

The initial segmentation is considered a soft constraint. It means that the initial segmentation is only a starting point for the subsequent computation which should find more appropriate segmentation, usually by minimizing some form of an energy function. On the other side, boundary indication and object indication are most commonly considered hard constraints. For boundary indication this means that

the final boundary of an object has to include user defined points. For object indication this means that the areas of an image that a user marked with certain label must have the same label in the computed segmentation. However there exist methods, which consider e.g. the object indication only a soft constraint [3, 29].

2.2 Desired properties

Leo Grady proposed [16] four properties which a practical interactive segmentation algorithm has to satisfy:

1. Fast computation
2. Fast editing
3. An ability to produce an arbitrary segmentation with enough user interaction
4. Intuitive segmentations

The first two requirements are obvious prerequisites for the interactive technique to be comfortable for the user and, most importantly, useful. Ideally, the computation of the algorithm should be so fast that the user is able to observe changes instantaneously. At the same time, the user should be able to quickly edit their input in order to change the segmentation which does not reflect the desired result. In case the computation or editing is too time-consuming, it may eventually be better and faster to segment the image manually (see Section 1.1).

The third requirement mentions an ability to produce an arbitrary segmentation. Ideally, the algorithm should require only little information from a user in order to compute good segmentation. In some cases it is nevertheless possible, that an algorithm returns results that are very different from what the user intended when providing their input. In such cases it is necessary to have full control over the segmentation and to have an option to obtain desired segmentation even if it was necessary to delimit some parts manually.

In the ideal case, the segmentation system should return results that correspond with users intentions and the user should understand

how their input affects the output of the algorithm. If the technique was not intuitive or properly understood, it is possible that the user would use the technique in a wrong way and eventually only lost their time.

2.3 Overview of state-of-the-art methods

Since image segmentation is one of the fundamental problems of image processing, there is still very active research, which brings new methods also to the category of semi-automatic segmentation. Because of a large number of known techniques and the fact that new ones are still emerging, it is not possible to mention all of them. It is also not straightforward to classify these techniques, because some of them combine more segmentation approaches and therefore do not strictly belong to only one category. This section provides a brief overview of some well-known methods for semi-automatic segmentation and follows the classification of [18]. Several examples of segmentation techniques along with their brief description are listed for each category. Some of the mentioned methods are implemented and are described in detail in Section 2.4.

2.3.1 Graph-cut methods

Basic idea of graph cut methods is to construct a weighted graph, where vertices correspond to image pixels. Additionally, there are two more vertices representing foreground and background. After constructing the graph, the minimum cut is computed which defines the segmentation. The main difference between these methods is in the way how the edge weights are defined. All listed methods provide binary segmentation.

Interactive Graph Cuts [4] is a technique, which set the foundation and inspired authors of many other methods. It requires the user to mark foreground and background areas of the image with a brush, computes histograms of these marked areas and then sets weights of edges according to these histograms and values of neighboring pixels. This technique is detailed in Section 2.4.2.

Geodesic Graph Cut [31] additionally takes into consideration geodesic distance between pixels in order to avoid shortcutting problem, which causes the final boundary to cut through object interior.

Lazy Snapping algorithm [24] operates on an over-segmented image, obtained by the watershed algorithm [40]. A user marks certain regions as foreground or background. A graph is constructed, where each vertex corresponds to one superpixel from the over-segmented image. A minimum cut is computed to obtain initial segmentation. Lazy snapping authors also proposed a technique to manually refine object boundary on pixel level for cases when the superpixel based segmentation is not precise.

GrabCut [32] extends Interactive Graph Cuts with an iterative process and modeling the background and foreground distributions with Gaussian Mixture Models [11]. It also differs from Interactive Graph Cuts in the form of user interaction. In GrabCut, only a rectangle enclosing the object of interest is required. This technique is thoroughly described in Section 2.4.3.

2.3.2 Edge-based methods

Segmentation techniques based on edge detection rely on the presence of discontinuities in an image in a form of abrupt changes in intensity values. Edge detection algorithms try to detect points with sharp intensity changes in context of their neighborhood. Such points form edges, where the term "edge" refers to a boundary between two regions.

Live wire [27, 19] is a method, known from popular graphics software such as Adobe Photoshop or GIMP. First, a graph is constructed from image pixels. Then a user traces object's boundary with a mouse and provides points on the boundary by clicking. The part of boundary between provided points is computed as the shortest path on the underlying graph.

Active contour method [20] starts with a user defined initial boundary (contour), that is later iteratively changed by minimizing an energy functional. The goal is to find a contour, that minimizes the energy functional, which is a combination of internal and external forces. External forces attract the contour toward the edges, whereas

internal forces help to keep the contour smooth. The initial contour should be close to the real edges, otherwise the external forces could be too small to attract it. **Gradient Vector Flow** (GVF) model [45] tries to address this problem by employing GVF field that helps to attract the contour to edges even when they are distant. Another advantage is that GVF model improves performance when the final contour should have a concave shape. Other approach that addresses issues of the classic model is the **Balloon model** [8], which adds another force that "inflates" the contour.

2.3.3 Random walks methods

Random walks methods provide K-ary segmentation and are based on the idea of a random walker walking on a graph constructed from the image. A user first labels selected pixels with any of K labels. In the classic **Random Walks** technique by Grady [16], which is described in detail in Section 2.4.4, the final label of each pixel is determined in this way: starting at each pixel, what is the label of the seed point that random walker is most likely to reach first.

Random Walks with Restart technique [21] add restarting probability. Random walker starts at seed points and at each point of his way, there is a probability that he returns back to the starting point. Final label of each pixel is determined by maximum probability that a walker stays at this point, supposed he started from a seed point with certain label.

2.3.4 Region-based methods

The objective of region based segmentation techniques is to partition an image into homogeneous regions. These methods work with an assumption that pixels inside one region share particular characteristic, such as intensity or color. Two common approaches are region growing and region splitting. Region growing starts with initial seed region, which is iteratively merged with its neighbors that satisfy defined similarity criterion. Region splitting approach starts with the whole image as the initial region. Regions are iteratively split until all sub-regions are homogeneous. These two approaches can be combined to achieve better results.

Seeded Region Growing [1] is a technique providing K-ary segmentation. A user first marks selected pixels with any of K labels. Areas initially marked by the user then iteratively grow by including neighboring pixels. If a pixel, that is yet unlabeled, neighbors with more than one labeled region, it is included to the region, whose mean value is closer to the pixel value. The algorithm iterates until all pixels are labeled.

GrowCut technique [39] provides K-ary segmentation. User initially labels selected pixels which form initial regions. The image is modeled as a cellular automaton and labels are iteratively propagated to their neighborhood based on the strength of the label and similarity of the neighboring pixels.

Maximal Similarity Based Region Merging [28] works with an over-segmented image, which can result from Mean shift [15] or another similar clustering algorithm. A user marks selected regions as foreground or background. Then, unmarked regions neighboring with background regions are merged with background regions respecting the following rule: Let B a background region and M be its neighboring region. If B is the most similar to M among all neighbors of M , then merge M with B . This way, starting from the marked background regions, all regions that meet the similarity condition are merged into one. Then the algorithm starts merging from the remaining unmarked regions, which leads to the extraction of the foreground region.

2.4 Implemented methods

This section provides a theoretical background of four implemented methods: Interactive Graph Cuts, GrabCut, Random Walks, and a method based on a region growing approach, that will be referred to as Simple Region Growing. The selection of the first three methods was based on the fact that they are frequently cited and used to evaluate a performance of newly developed methods [16, 21, 2, 7, 23, 17]. Also, each of them works with different user input. Interactive Graph Cuts technique requires a user to draw foreground and background markers, GrabCut requires a bounding box and Random Walks technique requires a user to mark each object with a different label. Simple Region Growing method was implemented mainly to provide

a more convenient alternative to manual segmentation that should theoretically work well on images where foreground intensity is very different from the background intensity.

Definitions of some concepts that are used in the described techniques are presented first, then all implemented techniques are described in detail.

2.4.1 Definitions

Image representation by a graph

Segmentation techniques are often based on comparing or calculating some value from the pairs of neighboring pixels and therefore it can be often convenient to model an image by a graph structure, whose edges can have associated values. However the graph image representation is not only used by segmentation techniques. Also other tasks of image processing, that can be formulated as energy minimization problems, such as image smoothing, stereo correspondence problem and others, can benefit from using the graph structure. Image processing tasks that can be formulated in terms of energy minimization can be often computed or approximated by finding the minimum cut of an appropriate graph.

The image is represented as a graph $G = (V, E)$, where V is a set of vertices and E is a set of edges. Each vertex in V correspond to one pixel of the image. Edges in set E can be defined as 2-element subsets of V in which case the graph is called *undirected*. Another way is to define edges as ordered pairs of vertices. Then the graph is called *directed*. For the purposes of this thesis, graphs will be considered to be undirected.

The set E is defined by neighborhood relation on image pixels. $E = \{\{v, w\} \mid d(v, w) \leq r\}$, where $d(v, w)$ is an Euclidean distance between pixels v and w . In the case of two-dimensional image with square grid, $r = 1$ matches the 4-connectivity and $r = \sqrt{2}$ matches the 8-connectivity.

If there is a function $w : E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, which assigns each edge a real weight, then the graph is *weighted*. The weighting function w is usually defined in order to express relationship of the vertices (or pixels) that it connects. For example it can be based on the difference of pixel

intensities or colors. In order to find the minimum cut of the graph G , usually two special vertices, that do not represent image pixels, are added to G 's vertices. Both of these vertices are connected to all pixel vertices.

The degree of a vertex is defined as a sum of weights of its incident edges.

Graph Cut

Graph cut C of a graph $G = (V, E)$ partitions set of vertices V to two disjoint subsets S and T . The cut C of G is a set of edges, such that

$$C = \{\{v, w\} \in E \mid v \in S \wedge w \in T\}. \quad (2.1)$$

If there are specified special vertices s and t , then the s - t cut is a cut, where $s \in S \wedge t \in T$.

In an unweighted graph, the size of a cut is equal to $|C|$. In a weighted graph, the size of a cut is equal to the sum of weights of edges in C . A cut is minimum, if there does not exist any other cut with smaller size.

2.4.2 Interactive Graph Cuts

A segmentation technique, called Interactive Graph Cuts, proposed by Boykov and Jolly in 2001 [4], uses the image representation by a graph and an algorithm for finding the minimum graph cuts. This technique provides only a binary segmentation, therefore the output is a division of the image to foreground and background. Both foreground and background may consist of more isolated parts.

The interactivity of this technique is in the form of user providing information about the location of foreground and background parts of the image. The user is supposed to mark certain pixels that are a part of the foreground, also denoted as object, and some pixels that are a part of the background. This way the user provides hard constraints for following segmentation, meaning that in the resulting segmentation, all pixels marked by the user as foreground have to be included in regions labeled as foreground and pixels which user marked as background have to be included in regions labeled as background. By marking certain pixels as foreground or background,

the user does not only provide information about location of these regions, but also estimated properties of foreground and background regions can be extracted from the marked pixels.

Segmentation of the unmarked part of the image is computed by the minimisation of an energy function. Minimizing the energy function gives us the optimum among all possible segmentations satisfying hard constraints given by the user. The energy function depends on region and boundary properties of the segments and these properties are regarded as soft constraints for segmentation.

The image is modeled as an undirected graph $G = (V, E)$. Each image pixel is represented by one vertex. These pixel vertices together form set $P \subset V$. Let \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{B} be sets of pixels which a user has marked as foreground and background, respectively; $\mathcal{F} \subset P$, $\mathcal{B} \subset P$, $\mathcal{F} \cap \mathcal{B} = \emptyset$. Moreover two special vertices s and t are included in set V , resulting in $V = P \cup \{s, t\}$. Vertices s and t are called terminals and represent foreground and background, respectively.

The set E consist of two disjoint sets E_n and E_t . Each of these sets includes edges of a certain type. The first type are edges connecting vertices that represent neighboring pixels in the original image. The second type are edges that connect pixels with the terminals. Each pixel is connected with both terminals s and t . Edges between neighboring pixels are called n-links and form set E_n . Edges between pixels and terminals are called t-links and form set E_t .

The energy function is defined as:

$$\mathbf{E}(L) = R(L) + \lambda \cdot B(L), \quad (2.2)$$

where $L = (L_1, \dots, L_i, \dots, L_{|P|})$ is a binary vector specifying labeling scheme for image pixels. Each L_i can be either 0, if pixel $p_i \in P$ is part of background, or 1, if p_i is part of foreground. Vector L defines a segmentation and objective of this technique is to find labeling \bar{L} , such that:

$$\bar{L} = \underset{L}{\operatorname{argmin}} E(L) \quad (2.3)$$

The regional term R is defined as

$$R(L) = \sum_{i=1}^{|P|} \hat{R}(p_i, L_i), \quad (2.4)$$

where \hat{R} is an individual regional cost and will be precisely defined later. The cost \hat{R} depends on how pixel p_i fits in the intensity or color model of foreground and background areas marked by the user, therefore it specifies likelihood of p_i being labeled as foreground and background.

The boundary term B , is defined as

$$B(L) = \sum_{i,j:\{p_i,p_j\} \in E_n} B_{\{i,j\}} \cdot |L_i - L_j|, \quad (2.5)$$

where $B_{\{i,j\}}$ is an individual boundary cost and will be defined later. The boundary term B supports spatial coherence within areas with similar intensity and can be understood as a penalty for the case when neighboring pixels p_i and p_j have different labels. When p_i and p_j are similar in their intensities or colors, the penalty is large, on the other hand when they are very different, the penalty is small.

The presence of the parameter $\lambda \geq 0$ in the energy function allows us to specify a relative importance of regional term R in comparison with the boundary term B .

As can be seen from the definitions of the regional and boundary terms of the energy function, we have to define function \hat{R} for every pixel $p_i \in P$, and $B_{\{i,j\}}$ for every pair of neighboring pixels $\{p_i, p_j\} \in E_n$. The sets \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{B} of pixels marked by the user as foreground and background do not only serve as hard constraints for the segmentation process, but their intensity histograms are also used to estimate the intensity distributions of foreground and background regions, denoted as $Pr(I|\mathcal{F})$ and $Pr(I|\mathcal{B})$ respectively. For grayscale images, likelihoods of pixel with intensity $I(p_i)$ belonging to foreground or background, respectively, are defined as:

$$Pr(I(p_i)|\mathcal{F}) = hist_{\mathcal{F}}(I(p_i)), \quad (2.6)$$

$$Pr(I(p_i)|\mathcal{B}) = hist_{\mathcal{B}}(I(p_i)), \quad (2.7)$$

where $hist_{\mathcal{F}}$ and $hist_{\mathcal{B}}$ are smoothed and normalized histograms of user marked regions \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{B} . For RGB images, average colors of \mathcal{B} and \mathcal{F} are computed and denoted as $avg_{\mathcal{B}}$ and $avg_{\mathcal{F}}$, respectively. Then likelihoods of pixel with color $I(p_i)$ belonging to foreground or

background, respectively, are defined as:

$$Pr(I(p_i)|\mathcal{F}) = \frac{\|I(p_i) - avg_{\mathcal{F}}\|^2}{\|I(p_i) - avg_{\mathcal{F}}\|^2 + \|I(p_i) - avg_{\mathcal{B}}\|^2}, \quad (2.8)$$

$$Pr(I(p_i)|\mathcal{B}) = \frac{\|I(p_i) - avg_{\mathcal{B}}\|^2}{\|I(p_i) - avg_{\mathcal{F}}\|^2 + \|I(p_i) - avg_{\mathcal{B}}\|^2}, \quad (2.9)$$

Then \hat{R} is defined as negative log-likelihood:

$$\hat{R}(p_i, 0) = -\ln Pr(I(p_i)|\mathcal{B}) \quad (2.10)$$

$$\hat{R}(p_i, 1) = -\ln Pr(I(p_i)|\mathcal{F}), \quad (2.11)$$

where $I(p_i)$ is the intensity or color of pixel p_i . The boundary cost $B_{\{i,j\}}$ is defined as:

$$B_{\{i,j\}} = \exp\left(-\frac{\|I(p_i) - I(p_j)\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \cdot \frac{1}{d(p_i, p_j)}, \quad (2.12)$$

where $d(p_i, p_j)$ denotes the Euclidean distance between pixels p_i and p_j . The boundary cost $B_{\{i,j\}}$ is large for pixels p_i, p_j with similar values, but is small, when p_i, p_j are very different. The parameter σ controls size of the cost in relation to the difference between pixel intensities. Intuitively, by increasing σ , the cost gets larger and therefore larger intensity variation is tolerated within areas with the same label.

Each edge $\{u, v\} \in E$ is assigned a weight $w(\{u, v\})$. Weights of n-links reflect parameters of the boundary term, and weights of t-links reflect parameters of the regional term of the energy function. The optimal segmentation, which minimizes the energy function is obtained by finding an s - t cut with the smallest size on graph G .

A graph-cut partitions vertices of a graph into two disjoint subsets, in this case foreground and background. Foreground is formed by all pixels that are connected to the foreground terminal s and background is formed by all pixels connected to the background terminal t .

Since we need to satisfy hard constraints, which means that after partitioning the graph all pixels from \mathcal{F} have to be connected to s and all pixels from \mathcal{B} have to be connected to t , weights of t-links connecting s with pixels from \mathcal{F} and weights of t-links connecting t with pixels from \mathcal{B} have to be high enough to be excluded from the

minimum graph-cut. In order to minimize the energy function by computing the minimum graph-cut, weights of n-links are defined [4] as:

$$w(\{p_i, p_j\}) = \lambda \cdot B_{\{i,j\}} \quad \text{if } \{p_i, p_j\} \in E_n, \quad (2.13)$$

and weights of t-links are defined as:

$$w(\{p_i, s\}) = \begin{cases} \hat{R}(p_i, 0) & \text{if } p_i \in P, p_i \notin \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{B}, \\ M & \text{if } p_i \in \mathcal{F}, \\ 0 & \text{if } p_i \in \mathcal{B}. \end{cases} \quad (2.14)$$

$$w(\{p_i, t\}) = \begin{cases} \hat{R}(p_i, 1) & \text{if } p_i \in P, p_i \notin \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{B}, \\ 0 & \text{if } p_i \in \mathcal{F}, \\ M & \text{if } p_i \in \mathcal{B}, \end{cases} \quad (2.15)$$

where

$$M = 1 + \max_{i \in \{1, \dots, |P|\}} \sum_{j: \{p_i, p_j\} \in E_n} w(\{p_i, p_j\}) \quad (2.16)$$

After computing the minimum s - t cut C on graph G , the resulting segmentation $L(C)$ is defined as:

$$L_i(C) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \{p_i, t\} \in C, \\ 0 & \text{if } \{p_i, s\} \in C. \end{cases} \quad (2.17)$$

2.4.3 GrabCut

The general idea of GrabCut [32] technique is derived from the Interactive Graph Cuts algorithm. Both of these techniques segment an image by minimizing the energy function, which is done by constructing a graph with particular edge weights and successive computation of the minimum cut of this graph. Even though Interactive Graph Cuts technique requires users to provide only small number of scribbles in foreground and background parts of the image, the aim of GrabCuts' authors was to develop a technique, which

requires even smaller interactive effort. In order to perform GrabCut algorithm, the user is only expected to drag a rectangle around the segmented object. If the segmentation is not satisfactory, the user can later provide additional input by marking incorrectly segmented areas with foreground or background brush, in the same way as with the previous technique.

The main differences between GrabCut and Interactive Graph Cuts (IGC) are the following.

1. IGC uses histograms of intensities to model foreground and background. GrabCut uses a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM).
2. IGC computes minimum cut only once, whereas GrabCut employs an iterative process. In each iteration GMM parameters are estimated and then energy minimization is performed by finding the minimum graph cut.
3. IGC requires a user to mark foreground and background areas with scribbles. GrabCut requires only a rectangle with the possibility of adding scribbles if the segmentation is not satisfactory.

As a part of GrabCut technique, authors also proposed border matting algorithm – a mechanism for the computation of alpha values close to the borders of segmented object. If the objective is, for example, to extract a certain object from the background, with border matting, the object edges look smooth and when the extracted object is placed on different background, the result looks more natural. Since matting is not a topic of this thesis, the mentioned algorithm is not further described.

GrabCut uses GMMs to model color distributions of the foreground and the background. Both foreground and background GMMs are full covariance Gaussian mixture with K components, so in total, there are $2K$ components. Each pixel is assigned to one of these components, hence we introduce vector $\mathbf{k} = (k_1, \dots, k_i, \dots, k_N)$, where $k_i \in \{1, \dots, K\}$. This vector, together with vector L assigns each pixel a unique GMM component either from the foreground model or from the background model. Now the energy function depends on vector \mathbf{k} and parameters of GMMs, therefore it can be written as:

$$E(L, \mathbf{k}) = R(L, \mathbf{k}) + \lambda \cdot B(L), \quad (2.18)$$

where R is the regional term, B is the boundary term and λ specifies the relative importance of B with comparison to R . The regional term R is defined as the sum of individual pixel likelihoods of belonging to assigned Gaussian component with given parameters:

$$R(L, \mathbf{k}) = \sum_{i=1}^{|P|} \hat{R}(p_i, L_i, \theta), \quad (2.19)$$

where

$$\hat{R}(p_i, L_i, \theta) = -\log \sum_{j=1}^K \pi_{L_i, j} Pr(p_i | L_i, j, \theta) \quad (2.20)$$

and θ are parameters of the GMMs:

$$\theta = \{\pi_{l, k}, \mu_{l, k}, \Sigma_{l, k}\}, \quad (2.21)$$

where $l \in \{0, 1\}$, $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$. Parameter $\pi_{l, k}$ is the weight, $\mu_{l, k}$ is the mean and $\Sigma_{l, k}$ is the covariance matrix of k^{th} Gaussian component of foreground model if $l = 1$ or background model if $l = 0$. This means that $\pi_{l, k}$, $\mu_{l, k}$, $\Sigma_{l, k}$ are computed from all pixels p_i , where $L_i = l \wedge k_i = k$.

Because $Pr(p_i | L_i, j, \theta)$ is given by Gaussian distribution with parameters $\mu_{L_i, j}$, $\Sigma_{L_i, j}$, it can be rewritten as:

$$Pr(p_i | L_i, j, \theta) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi |\Sigma_{L_i, j}|}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} (I(p_i) - \mu_{L_i, j})^T \Sigma_{L_i, j}^{-1} (I(p_i) - \mu_{L_i, j})\right) \quad (2.22)$$

The GrabCut algorithm can be summarized in the following steps. Some of them will be further described in more detail.

1. A user provides an input by specifying a rectangle which encloses the object of interest. Pixels outside the rectangle form set T_B and are treated as known background. Pixels inside the rectangle form set T_U and are treated as unknown. The set of pixels representing known foreground T_F is set empty.
2. Pixels from outside the rectangle are labeled as background, that is $L_i = 0$ for all $p_i \in T_B$. Pixels from inside the rectangle are labeled as foreground, that is $L_i = 1$ for all $p_i \in T_U$.

3. Gaussian Mixture Models for foreground and background are initialized from pixels labeled as background and foreground respectively.
4. Each pixel from foreground ($L_i = 1$) is assigned to a component from foreground GMM, that is most likely to generate it. Similarly, each pixel from background ($L_i = 0$) is assigned to the most likely component from background GMM.
5. New parameters for both foreground and background GMMs are computed from pixels and their assigned foreground or background GMM components. All $\mu_{l,k}$ and $\Sigma_{l,k}$ for $l \in \{0,1\}$, $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ are updated by computing means and covariance matrices from all pixels p_i , where $L_i = l \wedge k_i = k$.
6. Graph cut is used to estimate segmentation, providing new labeling of pixels.
7. Steps 4-6 are repeated until the specified number of iterations is not reached or until convergence. Since the energy is minimized in each iteration, the algorithm is guaranteed to converge at least to a local minimum of the energy function [32].
8. (Optional) If segmentation is not satisfactory, the user can additionally mark some pixels as foreground or background. Foreground pixels are moved from T_U to T_F and background pixels are moved to T_B . Then, step 3 is performed once.

The initialization of GMM parameters in step 3 can be done in multiple ways. In order to learn initial π , μ and Σ of all GMM components, pixels in set T_U have to be divided into K clusters. The same goes for pixels in T_B . To accomplish this, we can employ K-means [25, 14] or Expectation-Maximization algorithm [10]. Another solution can be using Orchard-Bouman color quantization technique [30], which is recommended in [37]. K-means and Expectation Maximization were tested in implementation and a brief evaluation is described in Section 3.9.

In step 4, GMM component k_i of each pixel p_i is assigned in the following manner:

$$k_i = \operatorname{argmin}_{k \in \{1, \dots, K\}} -\log \pi_{L_i, k} Pr(p_i | L_i, k, \theta) \quad (2.23)$$

The graph construction in step 6 is done in the same way as with IGC, the only difference being the weights of edges. Weights of n-links in the constructed graph are defined the same way as in IGC (2.13). Weights of t-links are defined as:

$$w(\{p_i, S\}) = \begin{cases} \hat{R}(p_i, 0, \theta) & \text{if } p_i \in T_U, \\ M & \text{if } p_i \in T_F, \\ 0 & \text{if } p_i \in T_B. \end{cases} \quad (2.24)$$

$$w(\{p_i, T\}) = \begin{cases} \hat{R}(p_i, 1, \theta) & \text{if } p_i \in T_U, \\ 0 & \text{if } p_i \in T_F, \\ M & \text{if } p_i \in T_B, \end{cases} \quad (2.25)$$

where M has the same value as in IGC and is defined in equation (2.16). After the minimum graph cut is found, labeling vector L is updated.

2.4.4 Random Walks

Random Walks technique for image segmentation, introduced in [16], is based on random walks on a graph constructed from an image. Although this technique also uses graph image representation, it is in fact quite different from the graph cut techniques. In this case a graph is not directly used to compute a segmentation, like in the case of previous techniques where minimum cut is employed, however it is primarily used to represent an image and as a base for subsequent definition of other mathematical objects that provide means for computing the segmentation. Another essential difference is that Random Walker segmentation technique provides K -ary segmentation, whereas previous techniques based on graph cuts provide only binary segmentation.

The technique works in the following way. A user first marks selected pixels with labels, meaning that each object of interest should be marked with a unique label. It is also necessary to mark background area with one of the labels. These labeled pixels are called seed points. The final label for each unlabeled pixel is obtained by answering the following question: If a random walker starts at this point, what is the probability that he first reaches a seed point labeled as k . We have to answer this question for each $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$. This yields a vector $x_i = (x_i^1, \dots, x_i^s, \dots, x_i^K)$ for each unseeded pixel p_i where its each component x_i^s specifies the probability that a random walker starting from p_i first reaches seed point with label s . Let n denote number of pixels in the image. The final segmentation $A = (A_1, \dots, A_i, \dots, A_n)$, where $A_i \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ is for unseeded pixels p_i defined as $A_i = s$, where x_i^s is the maximum element of x_i . This assigns each unlabeled pixel to the label that the random walker is most likely to reach first.

Besides hard segmentation, this algorithm can be very simply adjusted to obtain fuzzy segmentation [41], because vectors x_i directly provide probabilities of pixel p_i being labeled as each of K labels.

The advantageous property resulting from the nature of this algorithm is that in the final segmentation, each pixel assigned to label s is connected through a path of pixels also assigned to s , to at least one seed point with label s . This means that each connected component labeled with s contains at least one seed point with the same label. This is generally not true for Interactive Graph Cuts and GrabCut techniques.

Even though this algorithm is based on an idea of computing probabilities that a random walker starting at each pixel first reaches a seed point with each label, simulating random walks would be computationally infeasible. However, the research has shown [36] the connection between random walks on graph and discrete potential theory, thanks to what the desired probabilities for each pixel can be analytically computed without the simulation of a random walk.

The first step of this algorithm is a construction of a weighted graph $G = (V, E)$, which is then used as a base for the following computations. Again, vertices in set V represent image pixels and each pair of neighboring pixels p_i, p_j is connected by edge e_{ij} with weight w_{ij} . The set V can be divided into sets V_S and V_U such that $V_S \cap V_U = \emptyset \wedge V_S \cup V_U = V$, where V_S contain seeded pixels and

V_U contain unseeded pixels. The main concept of this algorithm is a random walker, that visits graph vertices one after the other by crossing the edges that connect these vertices. Being located at certain vertex p_i , the probability that he moves to neighboring vertex p_j is given by weight w_{ij} divided by the degree of vertex p_i . Since the goal of segmentation is often to segment homogeneous areas that are divided by discontinuities in a form of high intensity changes, we want the walker to be more likely to cross from a pixel to another pixel with similar intensity, rather than to a pixel whose intensity is highly different. For that reason the edge weights can be defined similarly to the weights of n-links in the previous techniques:

$$w_{ij} = \exp\left(-\frac{\|I(p_i) - I(p_j)\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \cdot \frac{1}{d(p_i, p_j)}, \quad (2.26)$$

where $d(p_i, p_j)$ is the Euclidean distance between p_i and p_j . The parameter σ controls the weight in relation to the difference between pixel intensities. Intuitively, by increasing σ , the weight gets larger and a random walker is more likely to cross the associated edge.

The graph G is then used to define weight matrix W and degree matrix D , both having size $n \times n$. Matrix W contains weights between all connected vertices and is defined as:

$$W_{ij} = \begin{cases} w_{ij} & \text{if } p_i \text{ and } p_j \text{ are adjacent vertices,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2.27)$$

The degree matrix D contains degrees of all vertices on its diagonal:

$$D_{ij} = \begin{cases} d_i & \text{if } i = j, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2.28)$$

Then the Laplacian matrix L is defined as:

$$L = D - W. \quad (2.29)$$

It can be assumed that the vertices are ordered such that the seed vertices are first and the unseeded vertices are second. Then the

Laplacian matrix can be written as:

$$L = \begin{bmatrix} L_S & B \\ B^T & L_U \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2.30)$$

where L_S is a Laplacian matrix of seeded vertices and L_U is a Laplacian matrix of unseeded vertices. Then for each $p_j \in V_S$ we define a vector $m_j = (m_j^1, \dots, m_j^s, \dots, m_j^K)$ such that

$$m_j^s = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } p_j \text{ is seeded with label } s \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2.31)$$

Matrix M with size $|V_S| \times K$ is then formed by each m_j as a row. Matrix X , where each row is given by vector x_i , which defines probabilities that random walker starting from given point first reaches point with each of initial K seeds, can be obtained by solving

$$L_U X = -B^T M. \quad (2.32)$$

The final labeling A_i of each unseeded pixel p_i can then be easily extracted from the matrix X , such that $A_i = s$, where x_i^s is maximum element of x_i .

2.4.5 Simple Region Growing

The last implemented method is based on the idea of region growing, that is described in Section 2.3.4. A user first selects a point or a circular region, which represents foreground. The pixels neighboring with the selected area are then merged with the foreground if they are similar to the pixels in the user selected area. The degree of similarity needed for pixel to merge with the foreground is adjusted by user dragging the mouse closer or farther from the initial region. The farther the mouse is dragged, the more different can merged pixels be and therefore the foreground region grows bigger. Additional interaction option is to draw a "wall" that prevents the foreground region from growing over it.

A user first chooses a radius r , then presses a mouse button on a certain pixel in the image and keeps holding the button. At this point,

a mean intensity or color is computed from pixels that are within the radius r from the click point. Let m denote the mean value of this area. The next step is to compute a difference map D , that is an image, where the intensity of each its pixel d_i is defined as:

$$I(d_i) = \|I(p_i) - m\|, \quad (2.33)$$

where $I(d_i)$ denotes the intensity or color of pixel d_i from image D and $I(p_i)$ denotes the intensity or color of pixel p_i from the original image. By dragging the mouse, the user controls parameter h , which defines the allowed dissimilarity of pixels that are merged into foreground. The farther the mouse is located from the click point, the larger h gets. When the user drags the mouse and therefore changes h , the largest connected component is found, such that it contains initial region and for all its pixels d_i , it is true that $I(d_i) \leq h$. When the user releases the mouse button, the computation ends. Before marking the foreground region, a user has also an option to mark some pixels with the background brush and make a "wall" that prevents the foreground region from growing. This is achieved such that in the areas where the user draws with the background brush, pixels in D are set to a high value. Results for different h and a use of the "wall" is displayed in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Simple region growing applied to an image. Yellow parts mean foreground region, black parts mean wall drawn by user. Highlighted yellow point in the middle of the image is the point of a mouse click. On image (a) $h = 25$, on (b) and (c) $h = 100$.

The simplicity of this technique yields in a fast computation and therefore this technique provides a high level of interactivity, because

2. SEMI-AUTOMATIC SEGMENTATION

the intermediate segmentations are computed and displayed each time the user moves the mouse.

3 Implementation

Writing this thesis involved the development of an easy-to-use and extendible application for fast semi-automatic segmenting of a large number of images. In this chapter, we describe the implementation of the application. We specify the requirements on the application, comment language and tools selection, describe the design and architecture of the application, and we provide notes about the individual implemented segmentation techniques. Four semi-automatic segmentation techniques and an option to segment an image manually were implemented in the application. The implemented segmentation techniques will be referred to as segmenters. The application was tested on operating systems macOS 10.13 and Windows 10.

3.1 Requirements

The task was to develop a multi-platform application whose graphical user interface would allow to quickly and comfortably segment a large number of images using semi-automatic segmentation methods with an option to segment image manually. It was also required for the application to be easily extendible by implementing other semi-automatic segmentation techniques.

3.2 Selection of the language and tools

It was required to develop an application, that would be extendible and easily adjustable to user needs so that it would be possible to achieve quick and comfortable segmentation of large number of images. One option was to implement segmentation techniques as an extension of some available image processing software. Other option was to implement a new solution. Following the requirements on the user interface adjusted for the quick segmentation of large number of images and easy extendibility, the latter option was chosen.

Since the application is developed mainly for the needs of the members of the Centre for Biomedical Image Analysis at

Masaryk university (CBIA) , the selection of the tools used for the implementation was based on what is commonly used and known by them. Image processing libraries developed at CBIA are written in C++ language, therefore the same language is used for the implementation of the segmentation application.

To develop multi-platform graphical user interface (GUI) applications, wxWidgets library is commonly used at CBIA, therefore in order to be able to easily modify or extend the application, wxWidgets [44] is used to build the GUI. The wxWidgets library is multi-platform and uses a native API of given platform for displaying GUI components and rendering graphics. Although this approach has its advantages and applications developed with wxWidgets look and behave as native applications, it has also its weaknesses. Thanks to the usage of native components, it is not guaranteed that the application looks and behaves equally on all platforms. During the development process there was a number of issues and inconsistencies between the platforms the application was tested on. The biggest issue was a graphics rendering on Windows which caused problems with displaying image markers, intermediate segmentation results and bounding boxes, especially in cases when it was necessary to draw semi-transparent objects.

The i3d library [38] is used to work with images. This library provides structures and algorithms for working with images of different kinds and contains functions that implement selected image processing algorithms.

Since the two of the implemented segmentation techniques use energy function minimization by graph cuts, the Graph cuts optimization library [38], also developed at CBIA, is used.

For the purpose of the Random Walker algorithm, which works with large sparse matrices, the implementation uses the Armadillo [35, 33] library, which includes structures for the representation of sparse matrices, algorithms for fast work with them, and algorithms for solving sparse systems of linear equations. In case of using compiler with the support for OpenMP [9], some computations of the Armadillo library are parallelized. The Armadillo library also contains functions [34] for working with GMM, clustering algorithms K-means and Expectation-Maximization, which are used in GrabCut implementation and can be parallelized when OpenMP is supported.

3.3 Workflow

After the user opens the image they want to segment and chooses one of the implemented segmentation techniques, the first step is to enter the information that should guide the following computation. After the user is done entering the input, they can initiate the computation process, whose result is then displayed on top of the image. If the user is not satisfied, they can edit their input and run the computation again. At this point, the segmentation result is only available to the currently used segmenter. When the user is satisfied with the result, they can add the computed result to the final result that is shared between all segmenters. The segmentation process of one segmenter is shown in Figure 3.1. If the nature of the segmentation technique requires automatically repeated computation, the manual initiation of the computation step can be skipped and the computation can for example run automatically every time the user moves the mouse. This is how Simple Region Growing (SRG) works.

Figure 3.1: Workflow of segmentation using one segmenter.

3.4 Design and architecture

The most important class of the application is `Segmenter`, whose subclasses represent individual segmentation techniques. Each segmenter defines its user interface, handles user interaction, it is able to segment an image with particular algorithm and render the result. The `Segmenter` class will be described in detail in Section 3.4.1. Figure 3.2 displays the architecture of the application in form of a diagram with the most important classes and their most important methods.

Figure 3.2: Architecture of the application.

In order to easily add new segmenters, the user interface had to be designed so that it would be easily modifiable and so that it could contain user interface of variable number of segmenters, while each segmenter may need to display different user interface components in order to work properly.

The main component of the application is `MainFrame`, subclass of `wxFrame`. It defines a menu for opening and saving files and it contains two important components. The first is `ImageScrolledWindow`, a subclass of `wxScrolledWindow`, and the second is `wxRibbonBar`. The main purpose of the `ImageScrolledWindow` component is to display images, segmentation results and to receive user input in form of mouse interactions. The image inside the `ImageScrolledWindow` can be zoomed in and out and can be scrolled, when it does not fit the window. The `wxRibbonBar` component is used as a container for user interfaces of available segmenters. This component was chosen, because it is able to contain a variable number of tabs. One tab represents one segmenter and can contain different user interface components, therefore `wxRibbonBar` is suitable for the purpose of this application and can be used to extend the application with more segmenters. The user interface of the application is displayed in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: User interface of the application.

3.4.1 Segmenter class

Segmenter is a base class that is supposed to be specialized by specific segmentation techniques. It contains a pointer to an object of class SegmentedImage, that represents the image being segmented at the moment. This object is shared among all segmenters.

By practical testing, it has been observed, that in order to obtain satisfying segmentation result, it is often necessary to run the segmentation algorithm repeatedly with slightly modified user inputs. Since the images can have large dimensions and it is sometimes needed to only segment objects that cover small part of the image or it could be convenient to segment the whole image by segmenting smaller parts one after the other, there is implemented an option to mark the relevant part with bounding box. This way the segmentation is performed only on the bounded area and the rest of the image is ignored. Since the computation is performed on the smaller image, it is faster and therefore this approach can reduce the time needed for segmenting the whole image. Two of the important methods of the Segmenter class are

```
virtual i3d::Image3d<i3d::GRAY16> RunSegmentation(  
i3d::Image3d<i3d::GRAY8> img,  
i3d::Image3d<i3d::GRAY16> mask  
)  
and  
virtual i3d::Image3d<i3d::GRAY16> RunSegmentation(  
i3d::Image3d<i3d::RGB> img,  
i3d::Image3d<i3d::GRAY16> mask  
).
```

These methods are supposed to implement the computation step of the segmentation technique (see Section 2.1). Only distinction is that the first works with 8-bit grayscale images and the second works with 8-bits per channel RGB images. Parameters of these functions are an original image and a mask that could contain e.g. markers drawn by the user. The image and the mask are already cropped to include only relevant part of the image delimited by bounding box the user can optionally provide. The output is the segmentation result in the form of a labeled image.

Each segmenter has its own `wxRibbonPage` in which it displays its user interface. Each `wxRibbonPage` can contain one or more `wxRibbonPanels`. Each `Segmenter` primarily contains two `wxRibbonPanels`. One of them is common for all segmenters and include buttons for switching images, buttons for zooming in and out, button with a menu for changing how the resulting labels are displayed, and the button that displays the current label with a menu that allows quickly selecting the background label or a label that has not been used previously. The second `wxRibbonPanel` provides a space for buttons that are required by particular segmenter. The base segmenter adds these buttons to the `wxRibbonPanel`: the button for providing a bounding box, the button for removing the bounding box, the button for removing all markers provided by the user, the button for clearing the intermediate segmentation result, button for running the computation part and the button that adds intermediate result to the final result. All of these buttons are implicitly visible in all segmenters, but each button can be hidden by setting the appropriate boolean variable in the `Segmenter`'s constructor. By overriding method `virtual void AddButtonsToRibbon()`, it is possible to add more buttons or remove existing ones. It is also possible to add

another `wxRibbonPanel` that can include arbitrary components. Events triggered by the buttons in the `wxRibbonPanels` should be handled by overriding the method

```
virtual void OnRibbonButtonClicked(wxRibbonBarButtonEvent& event).
```

Semi-automatic methods can receive user input in various ways, but commonly the user interaction is done by mouse. Also, the mouse interaction can be of various kinds, e.g. the user can draw markers or delimit a bounding box. It is therefore necessary to distinguish, which mouse interaction type is used at given moment. The class `SegmenterMouseMode` and its subclasses serve this purpose. It is important to hold an information about the current mouse mode in order to receive correct user input and to render correct data to the `ImageScrolledWindow`. If certain segmenter uses mouse interaction type that is not implemented by its superclasses, it should extend the `SegmenterMouseMode` class with appropriate mouse mode and override methods

```
virtual void OnMouse{LeftDown, LeftUp, Motion, RightDown, Leave}(wxMouseEvent& event, bool insideImage) that accept an event as a parameter, that contains a position that is already translated to the image coordinate system, so it does not have to be adjusted because of zoom or offset of the image. The method virtual void Render(wxDC& dc) is used to draw information to the ImageScrolledWindow. If it is necessary to draw information that is not drawn by any of the segmenters superclasses, it is possible to do so by overriding this method.
```

Because all implemented segmenters can accept scribbles as their input, a class `ScribbleSegmenter`, subclass of `Segmenter` provides the functionality to draw scribbles with a brush tool. The brush size can be changed by clicking two buttons that are added by this class to the `wxRibbonPanel` or by pressing "F3" and "F4" to decrease and increase the brush width.

The `ScribbleSegmenter` class is further specialized by classes `BinaryScribbleSegmenter` and `NaryScribbleSegmenter`. The class `BinaryScribbleSegmenter` provides means to draw only foreground and background markers and adds buttons to switch between them. User can also use keyboard shortcuts "F5" and "F6" to activate background and foreground modes, respectively. The

NaryScribbleSegmenter that support drawing markers with arbitrary label adds buttons to switch labels that are used for drawing. Ribbon panels of BinaryScribbleSegmenter and NaryScribbleSegmenter are displayed in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4: Ribbon panels of the BinaryScribbleSegmenter (top) and NaryScribbleSegmenter (bottom).

To achieve better code organization, each segmenter has a companion class that implements the computation part of the segmentation technique. For example, GrabCutSegmenter implements the user interface, handles the user interaction and renders relevant information on top of the image. Its companion class GrabCutSegmenterBackend then implements the segmentation computation itself.

3.5 Features of the application

3.5.1 File handling

A user can open one or multiple images by selecting the menu item *"File → Open files..."* or all images in particular directory by selecting *"File → Open directory..."*. Opened images can be browsed by clicking on the *Next/Previous Image* buttons or by pressing left or right arrows on a keyboard. The result of the segmentation of the current image can be saved by selecting *"File → Save segmentation"*. By selecting *"File → Save all segmentations"*, results of segmentations of all opened images will be saved. Results are saved as a 16-bit grayscale images in PNG format into the *segmented* directory that is created next to the original images. The filenames are equal to the filenames of the original images.

3.5.2 Label features

The final segmentation result can be displayed in form of regions filled with label's color or in form of outlines of segmented regions. Segmentation result can also be hidden. Each of these options can be selected from the menu that can be displayed after clicking the bottom part of the *Show Labels* button. There are also keyboard shortcuts for these options: "F" to show filled regions, "O" to show outlined regions and "H" to toggle between hiding and showing the result.

A label that is currently used can be changed with keys "F1" and "F2". After clicking the *Current Label* button, a user has an option to quickly select the background label or a label that has not been used previously. Alternatively, these options can be selected by pressing keys "B" and "U" respectively.

When a user clicks into the image with the right mouse button, a menu is displayed where the user has an option to select a label that is used in the result at the position of the click by selecting the option *Select this label*. This menu also provides options to repaint component located at the click position with current label or repaint all components that has the same label as the component at the click location.

3.6 Manual Segmenter

Manual segmenter provides a possibility to segment an image manually, that may be convenient mainly in cases when it is difficult to use any of the semi-automatic techniques or in cases when it is necessary to manually edit result obtained by semi-automatic segmentation. Manual segmenter is implemented by class `ManualSegmenter`, which is a subclass of `NaryScribbleSegmenter`. It provides two tools for drawing into an image. The user interface of this segmenter is displayed in Figure 3.5. First tool is activated by toggling the *Stroke area* button and provides a possibility to draw into image with a brush with variable width. The second tool can be activated by toggling the *Fill area* button. User can also draw with a brush, but in addition after the mouse button is released, an area inside the drawn curve is filled. Everything that the user draws is automatically added to the final segmentation result.

Figure 3.5: User interface of the Manual Segmenter.

3.7 Region Growing Segmenter

Region growing segmenter implements Simple Region Growing, that is described in Section 2.4.5. It provides two tools: *Wall* and *Seed*. Both of these tools can be activated by toggling corresponding buttons, that are displayed in Figure 3.6. When the *Wall* tool is active, user can draw a wall, as described in Section 2.4.5. After activating the *Seed* tool, user is supposed to click onto an object that is a subject of segmentation, and drag the mouse away from the object. As the distance between the mouse cursor and the point, where user has clicked, grows, the foreground region also grows. The distance between the cursor and the click-point is displayed above the mouse cursor. After the mouse button is released, the foreground is assigned the currently used label, that is displayed in the common part of the ribbon bar, and is automatically added to the final segmentation result. The wall drawn by the *Wall* tool is removed and user can start segmenting another object.

Figure 3.6: User interface of the Region growing segmenter.

3.8 GraphCut Segmenter

GraphCut segmenter is implemented by class `GraphCutSegmenter`, that inherits from `BinaryScribbleSegmenter`. It implements the Interactive Graph Cuts segmentation technique, that is described in

Section 2.4.2. A user can use three tools: *Background brush*, *Foreground brush* and *Bounding box*. Each tool can be activated by its own button. The user interface with all available buttons is displayed in Figure 3.7. Background and foreground brushes can be also activated by keyboard shortcuts "F5" and "F6". GraphCut segmenter adds an additional `wxRibbonPanel` with two sliders that can be used to set parameters λ and σ . User is supposed to draw on the segmented object with the *Foreground brush*. It is also necessary to draw on background parts of the image with the *Background brush*. When needed, user can enclose the segmented object with the *Bounding box* tool.

Figure 3.7: User interface of the GraphCut segmenter. For better readability, the common part of the ribbon bar is left out.

3.9 GrabCut Segmenter

GrabCut segmenter implements the GrabCut technique described in Section 2.4.3. It is implemented by class `GrabCutSegmenter`, that inherits from `BinaryScribbleSegmenter`. Four tools are at disposal in this segmenter. The first tool is *GrabCut bounding box*, that has the function of bounding box described in Section 2.4.3 and is supposed to bound the object of interest. Other tools are *Background brush*, *Foreground brush* and *Bounding box*, that may be used to run the computation on the smaller part of the image. First, a user has to place a *GrabCut bounding box* around the object of interest. Then a computation part of the segmentation can be performed. Then the user can use the background and foreground brushes to provide an additional input and then the computation step can be performed again. The user interface of this segmenter is displayed in Figure 3.8.

Implementation uses the Kohli&Torr algorithm [22] for finding minimum graph cut, that is implemented in the Graph cuts optimization library [38]. This algorithm was chosen because it uses a structure that can be stored between GrabCut iterations and allows dynamic changing of t-link weights, while n-links are preserved. This

Figure 3.8: User interface of the GrabCut segmenter. For better readability, the common part of the ribbon bar is left out.

approach speeds up the repeated computation of the minimum cuts and also saves time, because the n -link weights have to be set only once. Because the implementations of GrabCut and IGC share the same code, the Kohli&Torr algorithm is also used in the GraphCut Segmenter.

To initialize the Gaussian Mixture Models, as described in Section 2.4.3, K-means [25, 14] and Expectation-Maximization [10] algorithms were tested. Both these algorithms are available in the Armadillo [35] library and can be parallelized when OpenMP [9] is enabled. Computation times of these algorithm were compared on 10 RGB images. Then the results were compared using Jaccard similarity coefficient [43]. On 8 threads, K-means was in average $3,3\times$ faster than Expectation-Maximization, while the final results were very similar with average Jaccard coefficient equal to 0,9908. Since the results were very similar, and K-Means outperformed Expectation-Maximization in terms of speed, K-Means algorithm is used in the GrabCut implementation.

It was often the case that the covariance matrix of some of the GMM components was singular, which made it impossible to compute the likelihoods that a certain pixel was generated by a certain GMM component. To prevent this issue, a small value of 0,0001 was added to the diagonal of all covariance matrices.

3.10 Random Walk Segmenter

Random Walk segmenter implements the Random Walks technique described in Section 2.4.4. It is implemented by class `RandomWalkSegmenter`, which is a subclass of `NaryScribbleSegmenter`. A user can draw markers with a brush with variable width to mark the location of individual objects. There is also a possibility to use the *Bounding box* tool to perform the segmentation

computation on a smaller part of the image. `RandomWalkSegmenter` adds an additional `wxRibbonPanel` with a slider that can be used to set the σ parameter. The user interface is shown in Figure 3.9.

Figure 3.9: User interface of the Random Walk segmenter. For better readability, the common part of the ribbon bar is left out.

4 Evaluation

Usability of each implemented segmentation technique on different kinds of biomedical images is discussed in this chapter. For each image kind, one or more images were first segmented by manually tracing objects in the image. Then the image was segmented by each semi-automatic method such that the result would be similar to the result obtained by manual segmentation, but at the same time emphasis was put on the time consumption of the process. With enough user interaction, it would be certainly possible to obtain results very similar or even equal to the results obtained by manual segmentation. However the goal of this chapter is to compare practical usability of the individual semi-automatic methods and to find out, how much time can be saved by using them instead of manual segmentation and how the results obtained by different methods differ. The time spent by segmentation with each technique was measured and is reported for each image kind. The similarity of the results obtained by different techniques is measured by Jaccard similarity coefficient [43]. The usability of each technique for each kind of image is discussed from the practical point of view.

4.1 QPI image

In this section, segmentation techniques are compared on one image of 43 cells acquired by a quantitative phase contrast microscope. The image, together with the results obtained by all segmentation techniques is displayed in Figure 4.1.

Segmentation of this image is challenging, because it contains a lot of objects with unclear boundaries and certain parts of some objects are barely visible. The image also contains touching cells with hardly distinguishable boundaries. Generally, all techniques work very well for isolated cells with sharp boundaries. For isolated cells with unclear boundaries, SRG works very well, but IGC and GrabCut need to have foreground markers in the darker parts of objects, otherwise only the brightest parts get segmented. RW also requires to have seed points located close to the object boundary from the inside of the cell and background seeds close to the boundary from the outside.

Table 4.1: Segmentation times of the QPI image.

Manual	8,5 minutes
IGC	6,5 minutes
GrabCut	6 minutes
RW	7,5 minutes
SRG	7 minutes

Table 4.2: Jaccard coefficients of segmentation results of the QPI image.

	Manual	IGC	GrabCut	RW	SRG
Manual	1	0,7538	0,611	0,7433	0,7434
IGC	0,7538	1	0,7434	0,7534	0,7957
GrabCut	0,611	0,7434	1	0,6859	0,7464
RW	0,7433	0,7534	0,6859	1	0,7316
SRG	0,7434	0,7957	0,7464	0,7316	1

The most problematic part of the image are the cells that are tightly grouped together. The most comfortable experience in this part of the image was provided by RW which only requires to draw seed points in each cell and optionally background. Other methods required to segment cells one by one and required to "enclose" the segmented cell by background marker so that the foreground region would not "overflow" into the neighboring cells. Parameters for IGC and GrabCut were set as: $\lambda = 30$, $\sigma = 6$. Number of GMM components for GrabCut was set to 5. For RW, parameter σ was set to 5.

The time spent by segmentation using each of the implemented techniques is shown in Table 4.1. The time saved by using semi-automatic techniques is not substantial, which is mainly given by the larger amount of user interaction needed to segment the area with the group of touching cells. The Jaccard coefficient was computed for each label in the resulting images. Then average Jaccard coefficient was computed for each pair of resulting labeled images. These coefficients are shown in Table 4.2. The result of IGC segmentation is the most

similar to the result of manual segmentation. Regarding only semi-automatic techniques, results of IGC and SRG are the most similar.

4.2 Angiogenesis image

In this section, segmentation techniques are compared on one image capturing Angiogenesis by a phase-contrast microscope. The image, together with results obtained by all segmentation techniques, is displayed in Figure 4.2. This image contains thin structures whose intensity is very similar to background and often, parts of the structures are not visible at all. This makes it hard to segment even by manual drawing.

All semi-automatic techniques did good work in the parts of the image with strong contrast, but thin structures that are hard to see had to be often drawn manually. Generally it is necessary to place foreground markers inside the light thin structures to provide the information about the position of objects we want to segment and background markers to the dark parts of the image. Part of the image with markers for RW is displayed in Figure 4.3. Parameters used for IGC and GrabCut were $\lambda = 80$, $\sigma = 2$. Number of GMM components was set to 5. For RW, parameter $\sigma = 5$.

The image also contains a large number of small isolated light objects that were often labeled as a foreground by IGC and GrabCut techniques and therefore had to be manually deleted afterwards. As can be seen in Table 4.3 which shows times needed for segmentation using each method, using any of the implemented semi-automatic methods can save 50 % and more time in comparison with manual segmentation, while the results are visually very similar. More exact comparison of similarity of results using Jaccard coefficient is displayed in Table 4.4. It can be observed, that the result obtained by manual segmentation is most similar to the result of IGC. Two techniques that provide the most similar results are IGC and GrabCut.

4.3 HeLa cells image

In this section, segmentation techniques are compared on an image of HeLa cells [42]. The image contains 10 cells and it is displayed

Table 4.3: Segmentation times of the angiogenesis image.

Manual	55 minutes
IGC	25 minutes
GrabCut	24 minutes
RW	27 minutes
SRG	22 minutes

Table 4.4: Jaccard coefficients of segmentation results of the angiogenesis image.

	Manual	IGC	GrabCut	RW	SRG
Manual	1	0,6929	0,691	0,6534	0,6797
IGC	0,6929	1	0,7227	0,6960	0,6726
GrabCut	0,691	0,7227	1	0,6763	0,712
RW	0,6534	0,6960	0,6763	1	0,6387
SRG	0,6797	0,6726	0,712	0,6387	1

in Figure 4.4 together with segmentation results obtained by all implemented techniques.

Since the contrast of the image is low, the SRG technique was absolutely unusable, because the image intensity inside the cells is approximately the same as the intensity outside the cells, but at the same time, the cells have higher intensity variance than the background parts. Because of this, the parameter h (see Section 2.4.5) had to be set relatively high so that the foreground region would cover the whole cell. This caused the foreground region to "overflow" to the background parts of the image even when the cell was not fully covered by the foreground region, as is displayed in Figure 4.5. It was necessary to draw a boundary of each cell with the *Wall* tool, therefore the SRG technique brought no advantage over the manual segmentation.

The IGC technique can work well for this image, if enough attention is given to the tuning of parameters. Parameter λ was set to 40 and parameter σ was set to 12.

The GrabCut technique could be used less comfortably than the IGC. Because of the low contrast and similar intensities in the foreground and background areas, it is not possible to properly separate the cells from the background using Gaussian Mixture Models. During segmentation, after using the GrabCut bounding box, almost each pixel inside it was classified as background and additional input had to be done with the foreground brush so that the cell pixels would be classified correctly. GrabCut required fewer scribbles to segment cells that neighbor with large background areas, i.e. the orange and two blue cells in Figure 4.4. Parameters were not fixed as it was often necessary to change them when additional scribbles were provided: $\lambda \in [8, 20]$, $\sigma \in [6, 12]$.

RW requires to draw a background marker from the outside of the cells. Since it is a K-ary segmentation technique, it could be used conveniently in the areas where the cells are close together. The σ parameter was set to 8.

The times needed to perform segmentation with all implemented techniques are displayed in Table 4.5. Interactive Graph Cuts and Random Walks brought a significant speed-up to the segmentation process. Although the segmentation with the SRG technique was faster than manual segmentation, the result is not as accurate because the

Table 4.5: Segmentation times of the HeLa image.

Manual	15,5 minutes
IGC	5,5 minutes
GrabCut	8 minutes
RW	6 minutes
SRG	12 minutes

Table 4.6: Jaccard coefficients of segmentation results of the HeLa image.

	Manual	IGC	GrabCut	RW	SRG
Manual	1	0,8835	0,8539	0,8938	0,8676
IGC	0,8835	1	0,8959	0,8912	0,8312
GrabCut	0,8539	0,8959	1	0,8405	0,8288
RW	0,8938	0,8912	0,8405	1	0,8647
SRG	0,8676	0,8312	0,8288	0,8647	1

foreground region always filled the whole area roughly drawn with the *Wall* tool, as can be seen in Figure 4.5.

Jaccard coefficients were computed for each label in each pair of segmentation results. Then an average Jaccard coefficient was computed for each pair of results. These coefficients are shown in Table 4.6. The most similar results were obtained by GrabCut and IGC. The most similar result to the manual segmentation was obtained by Random Walks technique.

4.4 Pancreatic stem cells image

Methods were tested on an image which contains 77 pancreatic stem cells. The image and parts of its segmentation results are displayed in Figure 4.6.

The image contains bright cells on a darker background, but some parts of certain cells blend with background, therefore it is harder to precisely delimit their boundary. Generally, it could be said, that

Table 4.7: Jaccard coefficients of segmentation results of the image with pancreatic stem cells.

	Manual	IGC	GrabCut	RW	SRG
Manual	1	0,4323	0,5552	0,4476	0,5217
IGC	0,4323	1	0,6959	0,7939	0,7123
GrabCut	0,5552	0,6959	1	0,7291	0,7258
RW	0,4476	0,7939	0,7291	1	0,7502
SRG	0,5217	0,71232	0,7258	0,7502	1

Table 4.8: Segmentation times of the image with pancreatic stem cells.

Manual	18minutes
IGC	9 minutes
GrabCut	13 minutes
RW	8 minutes
SRG	6 minutes

cells in the manual segmentation result cover larger surface, while semi-automatic methods segment only the brightest regions of cells. The fact, that results obtained by all semi-automatic methods are more similar to each other than to the result of manual segmentation can be observed in Table 4.7. The most similar results were obtained by RW and IGC.

The times needed for segmenting the image using each method are displayed in Table 4.8. SRG, IGC and RW methods can save a significant amount of time.

When segmenting with the IGC technique, only small markers had to be drawn in each cell and a very rough scribble had to be drawn in the background region.

GrabCut could be also comfortably used, because in most cases it was enough to place a bounding box around the cell. In cases when it was necessary to put more than one cell in the bounding box, additional scribbles had to be made. For both IGC and GrabCut,

Table 4.9: Segmentation times of the anthropod image.

Manual	9 minutes
IGC	1 minute
GrabCut	5 minutes
RW	4 minutes
SRG	4 minutes

λ was set to 40 and σ was set to 8. Number of GMM components was set to 5.

SRG could work very fast for this kind of image, since the cells are on a contrasting background and therefore it is usually enough to press a mouse button on a cell, move the mouse a little and release the button.

The fact that the background in this image does not contain any abrupt intensity changes, together with decent contrast of this image, makes RW technique easily usable. It was necessary to draw only very little markers inside each cell and few scribbles on background. Parameter σ was set to 12.

4.5 Anthropod image

Methods were evaluated on an image of an anthropod on blue background. The original image, together with segmentation results of all implemented methods, is displayed in Figure 4.7. Because the anthropod is the only relevant object in the image, also input markers of IGC, GrabCut and RW methods are displayed in corresponding images to illustrate the amount of interaction needed to segment the image.

Table 4.9 shows time spent on segmentation using each method. Interactive Graph Cuts technique whose parameters were set to $\lambda = 4$, $\sigma = 8$ was the fastest and required the least interaction of all methods. It was necessary to draw only one marker for background and one marker for foreground to segment the anthropod.

GrabCut required more user interaction with non-trivial amount of scribbles in the background area, especially in parts covered by a

Table 4.10: Jaccard coefficients of segmentation results of the anthropod image.

	Manual	IGC	GrabCut	RW	SRG
Manual	1	0,9467	0,9210	0,9430	0,9182
IGC	0,9467	1	0,9186	0,9638	0,9425
GrabCut	0,9210	0,9186	1	0,9278	0,9017
RW	0,9430	0,9638	0,9278	1	0,9289
SRG	0,9182	0,9425	0,9017	0,9289	1

shadow. Parameters were set to $\lambda = 78$, $\sigma = 16$, number of GMM components was 5.

Random Walks technique required to draw a foreground marker at each leg of the anthropod and background markers to the space between legs or its other parts. Parameter σ was set to 2.

It was necessary to use the Seed tool of SRG multiple times to segment the whole anthropod. When placing the seed area to the center of anthropod and dragging the mouse, eventually the background parts covered by shadow got labeled as foreground, while some parts of the anthropod were still labeled as background. It was therefore necessary to segment it part by part.

Similarity of each result can be compared by looking at Table 4.10 which shows Jaccard coefficient of each pair of segmentation results. All results are relatively similar. The most similar results were obtained by IGC and RW.

Figure 4.1: QPI image segmented by various segmentation techniques: (a) original image, (b) manual segmentation, (c) Interactive Graph Cuts segmentation, (d) GrabCut segmentation, (e) Random Walk segmentation, (f) Simple Region Growing segmentation.

Figure 4.2: Angiogenesis image segmented by various segmentation techniques: (a) original image, (b) manual segmentation, (c) Interactive Graph Cuts segmentation, (d) GrabCut segmentation, (e) Random Walk segmentation, (f) Simple Region Growing segmentation.

Figure 4.3: Part of angiogenesis image with RW seed points. Background seeds are black, foreground seeds are red.

Figure 4.4: Hela image segmented by various segmentation techniques: (a) original image, (b) manual segmentation, (c) Interactive Graph Cuts segmentation, (d) GrabCut segmentation, (e) Random Walk segmentation, (f) Simple Region Growing segmentation.

Figure 4.5: HeLa image segmentation with SRG technique. The segmented cell contains yellow round marker. The foreground region covers almost whole background part of the image, while the segmented cell is not fully covered. When the *Wall* tool was used, the foreground region filled the whole area bounded by the "wall".

Figure 4.6: Pancreatic stem cells image segmented by various segmentation techniques. Segmentation results are cropped to cover the top-left quarter of the image, so that the differences are better visible: (a) original image, (b) manual segmentation, (c) Interactive Graph Cuts segmentation, (d) GrabCut segmentation, (e) Random Walk segmentation, (f) Simple Region Growing segmentation.

Figure 4.7: Image of an anthropoid segmented by various segmentation techniques. Segmentation results are cropped. (a) original image, (b) manual segmentation, (c) Interactive Graph Cuts segmentation with markers, (d) GrabCut segmentation with bounding box and additional markers, (e) Random Walk segmentation with markers, (f) Simple Region Growing segmentation.

Conclusion

This thesis deals with tools for semi-automatic segmentation. We described some of the well known techniques for semi-automatic segmentation and selected four of them for further inspection. A practical part involved development of an easy-to-use application for quick segmentation of large number of images. We implemented an option to manually segment images and four semi-automatic techniques: Interactive Graph Cuts, GrabCut, Random Walks and Simple Region Growing. These methods are described in detail in Chapter 2 and the implementation of the application is described in Chapter 3.

We tested implemented segmentation techniques on five kinds of biomedical images in order to compare methods' practical usability. Each method was evaluated in terms of speed and output of all methods was pairwise compared with each other by using Jaccard similarity coefficient. Even though methods were tested by single user on a limited number of images, it is possible to mention several observations for each semi-automatic method.

It was observed that all methods generally work well on isolated objects with sharp boundaries, while objects with unclear boundaries are usually challenging. Since Interactive Graph Cuts and GrabCut are binary segmentation methods, they often fail when the goal is to segment multiple touching objects. It is usually necessary to place a background marker between the touching objects or at one of the objects, otherwise they could be merged together. On the other hand, Random Walks technique may work well in these situations, since it is possible to mark each object with different label.

When using IGC, it is often enough to place only one foreground marker anywhere inside the object and one background marker outside the object to segment it. On the other hand, in the case of unclear boundaries, it is necessary to place the foreground marker close to the boundary.

Even though GrabCut was developed to simplify the user interaction required by IGC, the rectangular shape of the bounding box is often inconvenient, because when bounding the object of interest, we often have to include another objects that we do not want to segment.

GrabCut also often cannot separate an object when its intensity is similar to the intensity of background.

Simple Region Growing performs well on objects that have low intensity variance even when they have unclear boundaries. When the object intensity variance is high, it is usually necessary to use the *Wall* tool.

We also measured time spent by segmentation of each image by each technique. The measurements show that it is possible to save time when using semi-automatic methods, however it would be necessary to perform testing with larger amount of users to draw more confident conclusions.

A How to implement a new segmenter

To implement new segmenter, it is necessary, to create a class that inherits from `Segmenter` or any of its subclasses and add it to the `MainFrame`, the main component of the application. For example to implement a new segmenter, that provides binary segmentation and takes scribbles as an input, it should be enough to extend the `BinaryScribbleSegmenter` class and override `RunSegmentation(...)` methods. It is also necessary to set segmenter's name in its constructor. This name is displayed in the ribbon bar.

```
#include "BinaryScribbleSegmenter.hpp"

class MyNewSegmenter : public BinaryScribbleSegmenter {

public:
// Constructor
MyNewSegmenter(int id, wxRibbonBar* ribbonBar, MainFrame* parentFrame)
    : BinaryScribbleSegmenter(id, ribbonBar, parentFrame) {
    _name = "MyNewSegmenter";
}

// Overriding methods
virtual i3d::Image3d<i3d::GRAY16>
RunSegmentation(i3d::Image3d<i3d::GRAY8> img, i3d::Image3d<i3d::GRAY16> mask){
    return mask;
}
virtual i3d::Image3d<i3d::GRAY16>
RunSegmentation(i3d::Image3d<i3d::RGB> img, i3d::Image3d<i3d::GRAY16> mask){
    return mask;
}
};
```

Then it is necessary to include the new segmenter's header file to `MainFrame.h`, create it and store it in the vector of available segmenters. In the constructor of `MainFrame`, just create a shared pointer to the segmenter.

```
auto myNewSegmenter = std::make_shared<MyNewSegmenter>(1, GetRibbonBar(), this);
```

Then store the pointer.

```
_segmenters.push_back(myNewSegmenter);
```

This is enough to create and use the new segmenter.

A.1 Guide on implementing a new segmenter

If you want to add a new mouse mode, such as the GrabCut bounding box, it is necessary to create a subclass of the `SegmenterMouseMode`. The `SegmenterMouseMode` stores all possible mouse modes and keeps track of which one is currently active. Only one mouse mode can be active at a time. Base `SegmenterMouseMode` has two modes: *Bounding box* and *None*. `ScribbleSegmenterMouseMode` then adds a *Scribble* mode. `GrabCutSegmenterMouseMode` adds a mode for GrabCut bounding box. When adding a new mode, it is necessary to override the `UnsetAll` method, which should set all modes as inactive and should be called only when right before activating some mouse mode. You should implement two new methods. One for setting the new mouse mode as active and one for determining, whether the new mode is active.

```
class GrabCutSegmenterMouseMode : public ScribbleSegmenterMouseMode {
    bool _grabCutBBox;
protected:
    virtual void UnsetAll() {
        _grabCutBBox = false;
        ScribbleSegmenterMouseMode::UnsetAll();
    }
public:
    void SetGrabCutBBox() { UnsetAll(); _grabCutBBox = true;}
    bool IsGrabCutBBox() {return _grabCutBBox;}
};
```

Then in the segmenters constructor, it is necessary to construct an object of this class and store a pointer to it.

```
if (_mouseMode != NULL) delete _mouseMode;
_mouseMode = new GrabCutSegmenterMouseMode;
```

Last step is to override `Segmenter`'s `GetMouseMode()` method with the right return type.

```
virtual GrabCutSegmenterMouseMode* GetMouseMode() {
    return (GrabCutSegmenterMouseMode*)_mouseMode;
}
```

A.2 Adding new buttons

To add new buttons to ribbon bar, override the Segmenter's method `AddButtonsToRibbon()` and add a new button to `_ribbonButtonBar` by calling `wxRibbonButtonBar::AddButton()`. Do not forget to call `AddButtonsToRibbon()` on superclass.

```
virtual void AddButtonsToRibbon() {
    _ribbonButtonBar->AddButton(ID_OF_NEW_BUTTON, ...);
    BinaryScribbleSegmenter::AddButtonsToRibbon();
}
```

Then to handle events triggered by the added button, override `OnRibbonButtonClicked(...)`.

```
virtual void OnRibbonButtonClicked(wxRibbonButtonBarEvent &event) {
    int id = _ribbonButtonBar->GetItemId(event.GetButton());
    switch (id) {
        case ID_OF_NEW_BUTTON:
            // React here
            break;
        default:
            BinaryScribbleSegmenter::OnRibbonButtonClicked(event);
            break;
    }
}
```

A.3 Drawing on a screen

If you need to draw additional information on top of the image, override the Segmenter's `Render(wxDC &dc)` method and draw to the `dc` with `wxWidgets` methods.

```
virtual void Render(wxDC &dc) {
    BinaryScribbleSegmenter::Render(dc);
    // Draw additional information here by using wxWidgets methods.
}
```

B Electronic appendices

An electronic appendix to this thesis can be found in the file DP.zip. This appendix is available in the Information system of Masaryk University. Contents of the appendix are:

- app directory
 - bin directory
 - * win directory containing an .exe file of the segmentation application with all required libraries
 - src directory with source codes of the application.
- img directory with evaluated images and their segmentation results

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